

ROLE OF YONIDHUPAN IN VAGINAL INFECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Sthanik Chikitsa Is The Special Local Therapy Mentioned In Ayurveda Classics In Different Yonivyapada (Genital Disorders), Yoniroga, Santatinirodha and For Maintainance of Genital Health. Different Types of Sthanik Chikitsa Mentioned Yonidhawan, Yonidhupan, Yonipichu, Yonikalka, Yonilepa, Yonipinda, Yonivarti, Yonidhoopan, Ksharkarma, Uttarbasti. Yonidhupan Means the Fumigation of Vulva and Vagina is the Special Local Therapy Mentioned in Ayurveda Classics in Different Yonivyapada. Gynelological Disorders Maintain Sterlized External and Internal Environment of Genitals. Drugs with Katu, Tikta, Kashay Ras and Laghu, Ruksha and Ushna Properties are Described by Ayurvedic Acharyas. Dhupan Dravyas on Heating Get Converted into Fumes Causes Dilatation and Oxidation of Blood Vessels and Increases Tissue Perfusion Leading to Antiseptic and sterlized Environment of

Vagina. Yonidhupana Having Kandughna, Krimighna, Vranropak Activities. Has Bacteriostatic, Antimicrobial Activities It Is Economical, Easy To Perform And Having No Side Effects. Vaginal Infections Like Atrophic Vaginitis, Candidiasis, Trichomoniasis, Yeast Infections, Unusual Vaginal Discharge And Sti Sexually Transmitted Infections Routinly we See These Patients In Opd Even After Having Allopathic Tretment They Are Recurrently Having Vaginal Discharge, Irritation. Ayurveda Explains The Treatment of Yonirogas Starts With Nidanparivarjan, Shodhan, Shaman and Sthanik Chikitsa. The Way Gudbasti Acts on Pakvashaya And Cures All The Chronic Disorders In Body Sthanik Chikitsa Have Direct Action on Garbhashaya and Treat The Garbhashaygat Doshas and Completely Improves These Conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Yoni Dhupan Means the Fumigation of Vulva and Vagina is the Special Local Therapy Mentioned in Ayurveda Classics in Different Yonivyapada, Gynecological Disorders Maintain Sterilized External and Internal Environment of Genitals. Drugs with Katu, Tikta, Kashay ras and Laghu, Ruksha and Ushna Properties are Described by Ayurvedic Acharyas. Dhupan Dravyas on Heating get Converted into Fumes Causes Dilatation and Oxidation of Blood Vessels and Increases Tissue Perfusion. Leading to Antiseptic and Sterilized Environment of Vagina. Yonidhupana Having Kandughna, Krimighna, Vranropak Activities has Bacteriostatic, Antimicrobial Activities it is Economical, Easy to Perform and Having no Side Effects.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To Study the Use of Sthanik Chikitsa Yonidhupan In Treatment of Vaginal Infections.

OBJECTIVES

To study sthanik chikitsa from various ayurvedic text articles

To study the procedure of sthanik chikitsa yonidhupan

To study probable mode of action of sthanik chikitsa

Dhoopan

Different types of Dhoopana drugs On the basis of origin “Avum Dhoopa Samutpanna Prajanam Hitkamyā / Nirdishtascha Agnidāivtya Jangam Sthavaraashrya //” (K.S.Dh.kalp)

1. Jangama: Animal origin (Hairs, nails, horns, sar- panirmoka etc.) Animal product contains a keratin like structural part that contains sulphur play a key role in disinfection.
2. Sthavara: Plant origin (Agaru, vacha, haridra, kustha, guggulu nimba etc.)
3. Minerals: Harital & Manahshila. These are the Sulphur containing compounds According to Acharya Kashyapa¹⁰: Dhoopa, Anudhoopa, Pratidhoopa.

All these drugs are collected and stored in air-tight containers like earthen pots and glass jars to maintain its original colour and volatile oil contents.

Properties of Dhoopan Drugs¹¹

Guna: Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna, Vikasi, Uragandhi,

Volatile; Rasa:

Katu, Tikta;

Virya: Ushna

Vipaka: Katu;

Karma: Shothahara, Krimighana, Kandughana, Vranasho-dhana, Vranaropan, Vedanashamaka; Mahabhoota pradhanya: Akasha, Vayu
Purpose of Dhoopana : Rakshoghana
karama : Dhoopan of bhesajagar, kumaragara, sutikagara, Shastra-karam-gruha.

2. Vyadhinashana 13: for Vranashodhana, Vranaropan, Kledashoshana, Krimihara, Vedanashamak, Durgandhahara etc.

3. Sterilization of asava and arishata. Kaala: “Dwiraha karyed dhoopam dashratram atandrita¹⁴”/ (Su.S.) Dhoopana is advised in morning and evening for 10days for 3-5minutes. Yoni + Dhoopana means fumigation of vulva and vagina. Yonidhoopana is a practical procedure in which fumigation of vulva & vagina is performed by medicated and disinfected smoke over the surface of yoni. It is indicated as Rakshoghana and Vyadhi chikitsa in striroga and prasuta. Vagina is preferred as a route of drug delivery due to its large surface area, high vascularity and permeability to absorb the medicated fumes or any medicated drug kept in vagina.

Commonly used drugs for yonidhavan in vaginal infections

Sarala

Yava

Guggulu

Bruhatiphala

Haridra

Daruharida

Sarshapa

Kushta

agaru

Mode of action of Yonidhoopana: Dhoopana drugs with katu-tikta ushan and aromatic properties when put on fire get converted into volatile medicated fumes. These fumes enter into smallest units of tissues of genital tract (due to sooksham-srotogami), dilates blood vessels and helps in oxidation of blood that leads to adequate tissue perfusion.

This antiseptic & sterilized environment helps in disinfection of uterine cavity, vagina & vulva; reduces PH & laxity of pubic muscles Thus helps in reducing pain, decreasing vaginal discharge, healing of wound & prevent growth of microorganisms.

CONCLUSION

Dhoopana drugs having katu-tikta, laghu-ruksha, tik- Shna-ushna properties and volatile contents proved to Be kandughna, kledashoshaka, vranaropaka, shotha- Hara, jantughna, vedanashamaka. Yonidhoopana Means fumigation of vulva-vagina has shown signifi- Cant effect in different genital disorders, sutika, sukha- Prasava and improves defence mechanism of female Genital tract by maintaining healthy vaginal flora. Var- Ious drugs has shown antimicrobial action against E.coli, Staphylococcus aureus, S.bony, Candida albi- Cans. Therefore, yonidhoopana has bacteriostatic ac- tion, economical, effective procedure and easy to per- orm without any harmful effects.

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